

Investigating the influence of urban density on liveability through the lens of residents in Pune city

Mrudula Mangalkar¹ and Dr. Pratap Raval²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Planning, COEP Technological University, Pune, India

² Professor, Department of Planning, COEP Technological University, Pune, India

Abstract

Urban density is a complex concept involving the interaction of various perceptions with respect to the transforming realities of the built environment. Most researchers refer to urban density as 'population density', which considers the number of people residing in a certain area of the city, naturally increasing the built density within that area. The increasing built density is seen to be reflected in the urban form of that area due to high-rise and compact new constructions in order to accommodate this increasing population. The evaluation of density in the Indian context strongly relies on the population density taken through census in the form of persons per unit area and building density provisions in terms of FSI. Both these density measures apparently are not adequate to understand the built environment or document the density changes to understand how the urban form performs.

Liveability is a subjective term, hence every individual shall have their own priority and perception about their locality. It is often resultant of the existing urban form and how it responds to the needs of people. The parameters affecting livability of place or a locality are used for evaluation in this research. The paper outlines various parameters that contribute to the liveability of a place. Through the people's perceptions, the findings shall be presented in order to understand if there is any correlation between the urban density and the parameters of liveability. This research shall also help in forming a decision-making framework for density decisions at the city or local-level for enhancing its liveability performance.

Keywords: urban density, liveability, built environment, people's perception

Introduction

Urban density is a complex concept involving the interaction of various perceptions with respect to the transforming realities of the built environment. 'Urban Density' is defined as the ratio of the total population inhabiting a given urban footprint and the total area of the urban footprint. (Shlomo Angel, August 2020) Urban footprint here refers to the urban built-up calculated through land-use land-cover analysis. It can thus be expressed as-

$$\text{Urban Density} = \frac{\text{Total population}}{\text{Area of Urban footprint}}$$

While liveability is a subjective concept, varying from person to person based on their demands and needs, thus can be understood in different ways. Jane Jacobs (1961) stated that people's liveability standards majorly depend upon satisfactory access to community facilities, adequate provision of essential services and presence of amenities within walking distances. In most research the quarter of a mile (500m) walkable catchment is a reasonable distance for determining access to public services and as a result for measuring how walkable a community is. Thus, in urban planning research, the five-minute walk sets a scope for collecting both quantitative and qualitative data at a human scale. (Panse&Raval, 2023)

Methodology

The research focuses on studying the density values and morphological development of the study areas and surveys to validate this physical observations. A selection of six study areas have been chosen for the research in order to understand the residents’ perception for the existing urban density in their locality. This study requires 3-dimensional mapping of the study areas using GIS software. The data required for this mapping is generated using Google street views and field observations. This 3-dimensional map of the area is used to understand and assess the urban fabric of the selected study areas. Based upon the urban density, urban density ranks can be calculated for the various wards across Pune city. On the other hand, residents’ satisfaction survey responses not only help in understanding the people’s perception of liveability in different densities but also validate the physical observations in terms of functions and thus liveability.

Selection of Study area

The pilot area selected for this survey was Pune Municipal Corporation (PMC) which lies in the Pune district, Maharashtra state, India. The boundary of PMC has been extended twice due to addition of new villages within the city limits. Pune city, in last two decades has seen tremendous rise in population, with increasing built-up area and compact-high-rise structures in order to accommodate the increasing population due to migration. The suburbs of the city have come up with high-rise structures, while old city areas have redevelopments that are high-rise.

Hence, it is increasingly important to study and address whether the various areas with Pune city are livable and further understand which area performs better and the reasons behind this perception. In order to study this, six areas across Pune city were selected for its morphological study and conducting surveys for assessing livability through people’s perception. These areas were selected such that there were- 2 areas with higher, moderate and lower densities each, according to the projected and available census data as shown in table (1).

WARD	NAME	AREA (HECTARE)	DENSITY (PER HECTARE)	POPULATION	URBAN DENSITY	DENSITY RANKING	SAMPLE SIZE (80%,10%)	TYPOLOGY
WARD 07	BHOSALENAGAR	81	81	6561	122	3	41	LD_BUNGALOW+ APARTMENTS
WARD 10	BAVDHAN	85	81	6885	127	4	41	LD_BUNGALOW+ APARTMENTS
WARD 31	WARJE	72	251	18072	273	6	41	MD_PLOTTED+ APARTMENTS
WARD 30	SINHGAD ROAD	83	340	28220	371	8	41	HD_PLOTTED+ APARTMENTS
WARD 16	KASABA PETH	70	666	46620	735	10	41	CORE CITY

Table 1: Selected study areas

Selection of Study areas

Study area 1: Bhosalenagar

The study area is bounded by Khadki Cantonment on north side, Pune University in the west, Aundh-University road in the south. It consists of residential societies of Ashoknagar and Bhosalenagar area. It is majorly composed of bungalows and low rise apartments. In the recent years, the area has seen many redevelopment projects, where bungalows and other low rise structures are replaced with mid-rise apartments. The tree cover is seen to be dense within the study area due to sparse development pattern. It is one of the prime areas of Pune city with good connectivity and proximity to Shivajinagar, Pune University, Khadki Cantonment, etc.

Figure 1: Selected study area 1- Bhosalenagar, Pune city with mapping of the buildings, trees and amenities within the study area prepared by author

Figure 2: Photographs showing the built fabric within the study area-Bhosalenagar (clicked by author)

Study area 2: Bavdhan

Bavdhan is one of the upcoming, fast-growing suburb along western border of Pune city. Besides, it also well-connected to Kothrud, Paud road, Baner, Aundh, Pashan, University, etc. It has direct availability of transport options to PMC, University, Hinjewadi, Pashan, Kothrud, Deccan, Market yard and Pune station. The area composes of high-mid-low rise apartments - residential complexes and bungalows. High rise development can be seen taking place along the highway. The area also includes the area of Mahatma Society, majorly developed under Town Planning scheme, consisting of bungalows and low rise apartments.

Figure 3: Selected study area 2- Bavdhan, Pune city with mapping of the buildings, trees and amenities within the study area prepared by author

Figure 4: Photographs showing the built fabric within the study area- Bavdhan (clicked by author)

Study area 3: Warje

The selected study area is bounded by Mumbai-Bangalore highway in the south while an arterial road connecting Karvenagar to Warje Malwadi in the east. It is bounded by Bavdhan Warje hill in the north side, giving sloping terrain to majority part of the study area. The area composes of bungalows, mid-rise and low-rise apartments and gunthewari development. The area is predominantly residential with major residential

complexes namely- Nadbrahma Society, Ishan Sanskruti, Audumber Society, etc. This area has seen major developments during the years 2000-2010. Major area of this locality being located at the foothills, there is a presence of an undulating terrain, with few houses built by cutting off the hill. Most mixed use and commercial building, catering to the residential area are present along the Mumbai-Bangalore highway and the arterial road of Warje-Karvenegar. Due to comparatively sparse and mid-rise development, the area has managed to retain most of the tree cover. Other than the canal road, the locality majorly being residential, has no through traffic, reducing crowding, congestion and noise.

Figure 5: Selected study area 3- Warje, Pune city with mapping of the buildings, trees and amenities within the study area prepared by author

Figure 6: Photographs showing the built fabric within the study area- Warje (clicked by author)

Study area 4: Sun city- Sinhagad road

Vadgaon Budruk-Sun city area is one of the many upcoming suburbs of Pune in Maharashtra. Major part of the forest, fertile lands were converted to apartments and other residential complexes. The study area is bounded again by Mumbai-Bangalore highway on one side, Mutha river on the other, with Pune’s major arterial road- Sinhagad road on the east. The area composes of high-mid-low rise apartments-complexes and plotted housing. The new developments within this area are constructed high rise due to increasing demand for housing and shortage of building space. These new high rise structures are observed to transform the built fabric of this area. The traffic congestion along the major arterial- Sinhagad road is seen to have increased in past few years due to increasing population within this area and increased through traffic coming from Dhayari-Nanded city and Mumbai-Bangalore highway, moving towards the core or other parts of the city.

Figure 7: Selected study area 4- Sun city - Sinhagad road, Pune city with mapping of the buildings, trees and amenities within the study area prepared by author

Figure 8: Photographs showing the built fabric within the study area- Sun city-Sinhagad road (clicked by author)

Study area 5: Kasba peth

Kasba Peth is the oldest residential part of Pune city with a notably dense fabric. The area predominantly consists mixed use, and building typologies of Wadas and row houses, with shops on the ground floor. The area also consists of various other old and dilapidated structures. Due to the goathan rules for constructions, the old as well as the new construction has nominal setbacks making the built fabric dense. The study area has been delineated with Mutha river on the northern side and Laxmi road on the southern side. This area consists of heritage structures such as Lal Mahal, Shaniwar Wada and Mandai, increasing its historical importance. Being the first residential area of Pune city, it has the highest population amongst all other areas of Pune city.

Figure 9: Selected study area 5- Kasba Peth, Pune city with mapping of the buildings, trees and amenities within the study area prepared by author

Figure 10: Photographs showing the built fabric within the study area- Kasba Peth (clicked by author)

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire was broadly divided into 4 parts, with the first, introducing them to the topic and capturing the background of the respondent such as name, age, gender, area of residence, typology of their house and a question about how would they like their locality to look like. The second part consisted of the set of Likert scale questions about various amenities such as educational facilities, medical facilities, recreational and sports facilities, open-public spaces, public transport services and basic services. Social characteristics such as safety & security, and built & natural environment characteristics were also included, followed by the overall rating for livability within their locality and their comments, if any further considerations. A 7-point Likert scale, being the most reliable form for marking the ‘level of satisfaction’ within the residents, has been used in this survey. A Face-scale was adopted for making it easier for people to understand and answer.

Survey data Analysis

All the responses were arranged across with parameters on the x- axis and respondents on the y-axis. Based upon the responses of residents, the mean of the ‘Level of Satisfaction’ was calculated using the following formulae-

$$\text{‘Level of Satisfaction’ for the parameter} = \frac{\left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n i_k}{n}\right)}{7} * 100$$

Where,

i = ‘Level of Satisfaction’ given by individual respondents for each parameter;

k = individual respondents;

n = total number of respondents;

$\left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n i_k}{n}\right)$ = mean of the ‘Level of Satisfaction’ given by individuals

Survey responses

No.	Parameters for Livability		Level of Satisfaction (average) : Resident’s perception				
			Area 1	Area 2	Area 3	Area 4	Area 5
1	Educational Facilities	Availability	5.8	5.4	4.9	4.9	5.0
		Ease Of Access	5.4	5.2	4.4	4.4	4.4
		Quality	6.1	5.4	4.8	5.1	4.7
2	Medical Facilities	Availability	5.3	5.6	5.5	5.3	5.6
		Ease Of Access	5.5	5.4	4.8	5.1	4.9
		Quality	5.2	5.4	5.5	5.0	5.1
3	Sports Facilities	Availability	5.6	4.8	5.1	4.3	4.3
		Ease Of Access	5.3	4.9	5.0	4.4	4.0
		Quality	5.5	5.1	5.2	4.1	4.4
4	Entertainment Facilities	Availability	5.7	4.4	4.5	4.2	4.9
		Ease Of Access	4.8	4.5	4.6	4.0	4.9
		Quality	5.4	4.9	5.1	4.1	5.0
5	Open-Community Spaces	Availability	4.8	5.4	5.9	4.4	5.2
		Ease Of Access	4.8	5.4	5.6	4.3	5.3
		Quality	4.9	5.4	5.4	4.1	5.2
6	Public Transport	Availability	5.4	4.9	4.7	5.1	5.0
		Ease Of Access	5.6	4.8	6.1	4.9	4.9
7	Basic Services	Water supply	6.2	5.8	5.8	4.9	4.8
		Solid Waste Disposal	5.9	5.5	5.6	5.0	4.7
		Drainage	6.2	5.6	5.3	5.1	4.3
8	Road Safety	Pedestrian Safety	5.2	5.3	6.1	4.5	3.9
		Drivers Safety	4.8	5.3	5.7	4.7	3.8
9	Security	Day Time	5.5	5.8	6.1	5.5	4.3
		Night Time	4.7	5.7	6.3	5.5	4.1
10	Social Interaction	Privacy	6.3	5.7	6.0	5.2	5.1
		Social Cohesion	5.7	5.2	4.5	5.2	4.9
		Diversity	5.3	5.0	4.6	5.0	4.7

11	Built and Natural Environmental Characteristics	Housing Typologies	5.6	5.0	5.6	4.9	4.3
		Tree Cover	6.4	5.1	5.9	4.4	3.6
		Natural Elements	4.3	4.4	5.2	3.7	3.5
		Noise-Levels	4.9	4.7	5.4	4.3	3.9
		Air Quality	5.2	5.1	6.1	4.6	3.9
		Natural Light	6.1	5.3	6.1	4.7	4.7
		Cleanliness	5.9	5.5	5.9	5.0	4.0
		Visual Character	5.6	5.3	5.4	4.5	4.1
Overall Rating for existing livability		6.1	5.9	6.1	5.7	4.8	
Liveability Score based on survey responses		186.4	187.6	185.8	168.9	160.1	

Observations and findings

In study area 1 (Bhosalenagar), basic services, privacy within the locality, existing tree cover and presence of natural light in their houses were the highly rated parameters. Existing trees are seen to be responsible for better quality of air and enhanced level of comfort while walking within the locality. The low rise structures not only provide ample privacy, but also have positive impacts on various other factors such as reduced noise-levels, reduced traffic within residential area and natural light within the built structures.

Figure 11: Photographs clicked within the locality of Bhosalenagar (Source- Author)

On the other hand, being majorly residential area, there are less number educational, medical and leisure facilities within or in close proximity of the locality. On the other hand, in the study area 2 (Bavdhan), the air quality within this locality got the lowest rating in terms of being desirable. Especially due to increasing high rise structures and traffic congestion, it has resulted in the degradation of the air quality within the newly built areas in the locality. On the other hand, the area has adequate educational and medical facilities, presence of open and recreational spaces for residents, making it more convenient for residents in their day-to-day life. The old residents complaint about the increasing high rise constructions which not only lead to crowding but also have other issues such increased noise-levels, load on the existing infrastructure, reduced number of trees, view blocking due to higher buildings, etc.

Figure 12: Photographs clicked within the locality of Bavdhan (Source- Author)

In study area 3 (Warje), availability of basic services and social cohesion within the locality were amongst the highly rated parameters, while ease of access to facilities and availability of entertainment facilities were comparatively rated lower. The area lacks continuous footpaths and undulating terrain within the locality impacting the ease of access by walking. The residents within the locality are highly satisfied with the social characteristics of locality such as safety, security along with built and natural characteristics of the environment in the locality.

Figure 13: Photographs clicked within the locality of Warje (Source- Author)

The locality is situated at the foot of Warje-Bavdhan hills, hence consists of slope throughout the area, this has marginally decreased the walkability and intermediate public transport availability affecting the elderly people and children in terms of commuting.

In study area 4 (Suncity-Sinhagad), presence of the river is seen to affect liveability of the residents. The river along this locality has been facing hygiene issues due to water pollution and open dumping along the riverbanks. The residents were highly satisfied due to the safety and security within their locality during both day time and the night time.

Figure 14: Photographs clicked within the locality of Suncity- Sinhagad road (Source- Author)

In recent times, there are new residential construction coming up, with 18-20 storeys or higher, changing the character of this area. These massive structures are observed to cut the views and natural light of the structures around it. The existing farmlands seem to be developed in near future, with high rise buildings thus rapidly decreasing the green cover within this area.

While in the study area 5 (Kasba peth), the river was again a non-appreciated natural element, creating inconvenience for the residents due to lack of hygiene and cleanliness along the river. It is noted that the residents staying in close proximity of the river have to face the undesirable smell arising due to this water pollution. The locality has very few trees, raising the residents concern. It has indirectly affected the microclimatic conditions and comfort of walking to the nearby places, making them hesitant to walk during the day time.

Figure 15: Photographs clicked within the locality of Kasba Peth (Source- Author)

Apart from these, due to large number of cars and two-wheelers moving through the locality increasing the traffic on roads, residents find pedestrian safety as a serious matter of concern. But, being part of the core city, the locality is appreciated in terms of availability of educational, medical and other facilities within close proximity.

No.	Study Area	Livability scores	Urban Density scores	Persons per hectare	Observational Conclusions
1	Bhosale-nagar	186.4	122	81	As tree cover, privacy, low density and other built and natural characteristics are highly prioritized by the residents, the limited availability of infrastructure and services in close proximity is observed to be overlooked.
2	Bavdhan	187.6	127	81	Due to existence of the bungalows and mid-rise apartments, the tree cover, less congestion and other allied characteristics are prioritized. Other than these, there is presence of adequate infrastructure and services in this locality.
3	Warje	185.8	273	251	The locality has low and mid-rise structures with good amount of trees cover. Placed away from through traffic routes, it has less noise and pollution issues. Due to these factors, the limited availability of infrastructure and services in close proximity is observed to be overlooked by the residents.
4	Sinhagad road	168.9	371	340	The new constructions in this locality are high rise, cutting off light, ventilation and view of others and increasing congestion. There is availability of infrastructure and services in close proximity is observed to be overloaded by the increasing population due to high rises.
5	Kasba peth	160.1	735	666	The locality has major vehicular and pedestrian congestion along the roads leading to noise and air pollution. There is lack of footpaths and trees along road making it difficult to commute during the day time. There is adequate availability of infrastructure and services in close proximity is observed to be overlooked by the residents due to other undesirable factors.

Calculations

Considering a scatter plot graph representation with urban density scores on the x-axis and livability scores on the y-axis-

Figure 16: Scatter plot showing relationship between Urban density and Livability

Spearman’s correlation coefficient gives a measure of the likelihood of one variable increasing as the other increases expressing direct association or of one variable decreasing as the other increases expressing an inverse association. Direct associations are indicated by positive values, and inverse associations are indicated by negative values. No association is indicated by a value of 0. The stronger the association, the closer correlation coefficient is to -1 or 1, and the weaker the association, the closer it is to 0.

Equation for calculating Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient-

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

where, D= difference in the rankings of two coordinates and n=number of points in the dataset

Figure 17: Calculations for Spearman's rank Correlation coefficient

Conclusions

The Spearman's correlation co-efficient for comparative analysis of these five localities is -0.9, which expresses a significant statistical relationship with negative correlation between urban density with livability in the case of Pune city. This implies as the urban density increases, the perceived livability is seen to decrease. The higher density localities of Kasba peth and Sinhagad road were seen to have lower livability as compared to other areas of Warje, Bavdhan and Bhosalenagar with moderate and lower densities. The research shows statistical significance in the relationship between urban density and livability in the case of these five selected localities. The survey results suggest Bhosalenagar, Bavdhan and Warje to outperform in terms of built and natural environmental characteristics and the availability of basic services as compared to Sinhagad road and Kasba peth. This clearly validates the inadequacy of the basic services and quality of built and natural environment getting hampered due to the need to accommodate the increasing population.

As mentioned previously, livability being a subjective terminology, further research may be conducted in order to understand the association of other livability parameters with context to the urban density of the localities and make further conclusions. It is increasing important to identify the density any particular area could hold while not hampering its function, and catering the residents' needs. These conclusions can together help in formulating a framework for consideration of urban density in order to enhance livability must be made in the planning process.

References

Ameijde, W. T. (2022). Promoting Livability through Urban Planning: A Comprehensive Framework based on the "Theory of Human Needs". *Cities, Volume 131*.

Anna Kovacs-Györi, P. C.-B. (2019). Assessing and Representing Livability through the Analysis of Residential Preference. *Sustainability, 11* (18) 4934.

Anwasha Mahanta, P. B. (2022). Urban livability and contextual uncertainties: An assessment of livability through the lens of urban dwellers in Guwahati, India. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development, Volume 6*.

Astolfi, V. D. (2020). *Quality vs quantity. Is it possible to quantify the quality of public spaces?* Milan: POLIMI Publications Catalogue.

- Carl Higgs, H. B.-C. (2019). The Urban Liveability Index: developing a policy-relevant urban liveability composite measure and evaluating associations with transport mode choice. *International Journal of Health Geographics* (2019).
- centers, A. S. (2021). Francisco Benita, Vyacheslav Kalashnikov, and Bige Tunçer. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City science, Volume 48, Issue 7*.
- Chiu, S. A. (2017). Livability in dense residential . *Routledge journal* .
- Dietrich, H.-H. C. (2019). Measuring Livability at the Neighborhood Scale – Development of Indicators and Methods for the Comparison between Neighborhoods and Best Practice within the Chosen City. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*.
- Dongsheng Zhana, M.-P. K. (2018). Assessment and determinants of satisfaction with urban livability in China. *Cities* .
- Kashef, M. (2016). Urban livability across disciplinary and professional boundaries. *Frontiers of Architectural Research* (2016) , 239–253.
- Kimia Ghasemi, M. A. (2018). The spatial analysis of the livability of 22 districts of Tehran Metropolis using multi-criteria decision making approaches. In *Sustainable Cities and Society, Volume 38*.
- Kostas Mouratidis, A. Y. (2022). What makes cities livable? Determinants of neighborhood satisfaction and neighborhood happiness in different contexts. *Land Use Policy* 2022, Volume 112.
- Kulatunga, M. T. (2019). Understanding liveability: related concepts and definitions. *Proceedings of the 8th World Construction Symposium, Colombo, Sri Lanka, 8-10 November 2019*, (pp. 578-587). Colombo.
- Lilley, K. D. (2009). Urban Morphology . In N. T. Rob Kitchin, *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography* (pp. 66-69). Elsevier.
- Nora Osama Ahmed, A. M.-H. (2019). A Critical Review of Urban Livability. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 165-182.
- Panse&Raval, I. P. (2023). Impact of Street Vendors on Urban. *Environment and Ecology Research*, 891-903.
- Rama U. Pandey, D. Y. (2010). A Framework for Evaluating Residential Built Environment Performance for Livability. *ITPI Journal, October - December 2010*.
- Rama U. Pandey, Y. K. (2013). Understanding qualitative conceptions of Livability: An Indian perspective. *IJRET: International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*.
- Shlomo Angel, P. L.-H. (August 2020). *Anatomy of Density 1: Measurable Factors that Together Constitute Urban Density*.
- Siddiq Amin, H. S. (2020). Residents' Perception of livability: A case study of Quaid-E-Azam town (township), Lahore, Pakistan. *PLANNING MALAYSIA: Journal of the Malaysian Institute of Planners VOLUME 18 ISSUE 3* , Page 273 – 288.
- Urooj Saeed, S. R.-u.-d. (2022). An Integrated Approach for Developing an Urban Livability Composite Index—A Cities' Ranking Road Map to Achieve Urban Sustainability. *Sustainability* (2022).
- Wenjian Pan, J. D. (2020). Chapter 20- Towards sustainable urban development: urban design informed by morphological patterns and ecologies. In P. S. Primit Verma, *Urban Ecology* (pp. 377-411). Elsevier.
- Xiaojin Liang, Y. L. (2020). Livability Assessment of Urban Communities considering the Preferences of Different Age Groups. *Hindawi Complexity Volume 2020, Article ID 8269274*, 15 pages.
- Zahra Khorrami, T. Y. (2020). The indicators and methods used for measuring urban liveability: a scoping review. *Reviews on environmental health*.